

A Simple Recreational Experiment of the 1970's Monkey Theory in an Inefficient Market

PRESENTED BY

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A Little Bit About Me & the Research ...

What is the research about? and where did the idea come from?

[https://www.forbes.com > sites > rickferri > 2012/12/20](https://www.forbes.com/sites/rickferri/2012/12/20)

[Any Monkey Can Beat The Market - Forbes](#)

20-Dec-2012 — Give a **monkey** enough darts and they'll **beat the market**. So says a draft article by Research Affiliates highlighting the simulated results of ...

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Prof. Burton G. Malkiel

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Burton G. Malkiel

“A blindfolded monkey throwing darts at a newspaper's financial pages could select a portfolio that would do just as well as one carefully selected by experts”

- A Random Walk Down on Wall Street

E.M.H

Some Important Terminologies ...

- **Efficient Market Hypothesis (E.M.H)** - States that markets are efficient, leaving no room to make excess profits by investing since everything is already fairly and accurately priced.
- **S&P BSE 200** - Used to measure the performance of the top 200 companies listed at BSE Ltd., based on size and liquidity across sector.

A Simple Summary on How the Research took place..

- Downloading the entire list of equity securities listed on 01-07-2007.
- Choosing 25 random securities for each basket. In total, there are 20 baskets.
- Calculating the net value of each basket (on 01-07-2007).
- Checking up to see how those randomized securities hold on till the date 01-04-2022. i.e., What was the last price of each share on 01-04-2022 ?, How many listed companies were de-listed ?, etc.
- Calculating the net value of each basket (on 01-04-2022).
- Calculating the CAGR of each basket - rate of return over 14 years.
- Compare CAGR against the S&P BSE 200 & Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES.

The Objectives of the Experiment ...

01

To analyze whether the results received are similar to that of previous research (i.e. where monkeys were able to beat the market). - an exception being that the study is being conducted in an inefficient market.

02

To calculate the CAGR (Computed Annual Growth Return) of each portfolio and benchmark it against S&P BSE 200 & Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES. This to see how many and which portfolios were able to beat the market indices and by what margin.

The Entire Research Design & Process could be viewed by scanning the QR Code ...

The following slides include the results of the research experiment...

PARTICULARS	INITIAL_INVESTMENT	CURRENT_VALUE	NO._OF_YEARS	PROFIT/LOSS	NO._OF_STOCKS	CAGR_RETURNS_(Per_Annum)
S&P BSE 200	24,651	84,128	14 Years & 6 Months	59,477	1	9.16
Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES	25,096.50	93,555	14 Years & 6 Months	68,459	1	9.96
Portfolio 1	26,108.81	27,626.47	14 Years & 6 Months	1,518	18	0.4
Portfolio 2	23,993.09	47,001.60	14 Years & 6 Months	23,009	21	4.92
Portfolio 3	27,563.13	73,966.50	14 Years & 6 Months	46,403	17	7.31
Portfolio 4	22,942.53	138,764.54	14 Years & 6 Months	115,822	20	13.72
Portfolio 5	25,779.55	54,902.55	14 Years & 6 Months	29,123	23	5.55
Portfolio 6	24,144.43	92,140.46	14 Years & 6 Months	67,996	19	10.04
Portfolio 7	23,464.19	95,425.46	14 Years & 6 Months	71,961	16	10.54
Portfolio 8	25,121.32	66,312.15	14 Years & 6 Months	41,191	19	7.18
Portfolio 9	23,971.60	47,496.44	14 Years & 6 Months	23,525	14	5.01
Portfolio 10	25,585.10	71,024.17	14 Years & 6 Months	45,439	17	7.57
Portfolio 11	24,159.98	30,620.56	14 Years & 6 Months	6,461	18	1.71
Portfolio 12	24,026.37	36,081.24	14 Years & 6 Months	12,055	17	2.95
Portfolio 13	23,422.10	36,991.19	14 Years & 6 Months	13,569	22	3.32
Portfolio 14	24,217.21	38,829.26	14 Years & 6 Months	14,612	15	3.43
Portfolio 15	22,785.35	61,586.40	14 Years & 6 Months	38,801	18	7.36
Portfolio 16	29,500.92	87,270.40	14 Years & 6 Months	57,769	22	8.06
Portfolio 17	23,266.25	69,422.62	14 Years & 6 Months	46,156	16	8.12
Portfolio 18	25,591.10	108,196.46	14 Years & 6 Months	82,605	17	10.85
Portfolio 19	24,516.00	61,323.97	14 Years & 6 Months	36,808	19	6.77
Portfolio 20	27,648.35	29,851.31	14 Years & 6 Months	2,203	16	0.55

Graph 1.1: A Summary of the Research Experiment with regard to its Current Value and Initial Investment

SUMMARY - INDICES & PORTFOLIOS

Source: Bombay Stock Exchange - Bhavcopy

During the period of study, the Stock Market had experienced 2 Major Crashes: 2008 Financial Crisis and 2020 COVID-19 Pandemic.

While selecting the starting period of the study (01-10-2007), the market was in a state of bull-run and the randomized stocks were picked up right before the 2008 Financial Crisis (this caused a lot of those selected-randomized-stocks to be delisted in a couple of years).

The earliest period of the Bhavcopy available in the official website of BSE was 01-10-2007.

Things to Keep in Mind ...

Conclusion ...

Among the 20 randomized portfolios, Only 4 portfolios managed to outperform the market in terms of indices (such as S&P BSE 200 & Nippon India ETF Nifty BeES). Thus, we could conclude that the experiment did not achieve similar results to that of the statement provided by Burton G. Malkiel (1989).

The only exception is that current experiment is undertaken in an inefficient market whereas the original 1970s monkey theory had been conducted under a strong efficient market.

Thank You ...

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19-UCO-557

